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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

“THE PARADISE OF QUEEN SIBYL” - THE LITERARY TRUTH ABOUT THE MAGICAL DOORS SET BENEATH MOUNT SIBYL¹

1. Was Antoine de la Sale original? The lashing scourges, the slamming gate, the veils of fire and ice

When you take Antoine de La Sale's famous fifteenth-century text *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* and consider the page where the author describes the ever-slamming metal doors, hidden beneath the mysterious peak of Mount Sibyl, in Italy, the feeling of a truly magical adventure seizes your heart, and the legend of the Apennine Sibyl wins one additional soul to its ancient spell:

«... within that cave, up to the metal doors, which slam ceaselessly day and night, opening wide and then shutting close again [...] in the cavern, there are two doors made of metal, slamming day and night without rest [...] These doors slam so savagely that everyone who wishes to enter is made aware that nobody can get in without being caught between them and crushed like a small fly. And that was what frightened them the more...».

[In the original French text: «... dedans ceste cave, jusques es portes de metall, qui jour et nuyt et sans ceser battent, cloant et ouvrant [...] à l'endroit de la cave, sont les deux portes de metal, qui jour et nuyt batent sans cesser [...] Ces portes batent par telle maniere qu'il est proprement advis à celluy qui entrer y doit, qui'il n'y pourroit entrer sans estre entre

¹ Released on January 28th, February 3rd and 11th 2018
(http://www.italianwriter.it/TheApennineSibyl/TheApennineSibyl_LegendOrigin.asp)

deux cueilly et tout effroissé comme une mousche. Et ce fut la chose qui le plus espouvanta...»].

For centuries, this description has stricken the fancy of people all across Europe: the metal doors, living a life of their own, guarded the access to the enchanted subterranean realm of Queen Sibyl, with all her riches, handsome damsels and evil intentions. Knights and noblemen and adventurers flocked to the cave on the cliff of Mount Sibyl hoping to find a way to get into that darkness, go through the magically narrow bridge and beyond the wizardry of the metal doors, to the unchaste oracle who presided over the hidden kingdom.

Fig. 1 - An artist's impression of the magical doors described by Antoine de la Sale as being present within the cave of the Apennine Sibyl in Italy (composite picture by Michele Sanvico)

But was Antoine de la Sale sincere when he reported the story of the slamming doors in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*?

Or, maybe, did he just borrow - from some older literary source - another nice idea appropriately shaped to please his courtly audience - just like the narrow bridge whose concept was actually taken from an illustrious lineage of ancient “test bridges” for the judgment of human souls? Did he take the doors from the *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*, or the *Vision of St. Adamnán*, or any other antique manuscripts telling the tales of supernatural journeys into the other world?

Again, Antoine de la Sale was not original in his description of the metal doors. Something very similar already existed, spanning across a long line of older literary works.

A first suspicion may arise in our minds when we consider, for instance, *Huon of Bordeaux*, a thirteenth-century epic poem. In a previous article, we already saw that the poem contains an episode, set by a magical tower, which appears to be very close to de La Sale's posterior narration:

«Two men are standing at the gate; they are made of bronze, each man holding a double scourge, all made of metal and terror-inspiring. They never stop striking and lashing to and from, throughout summer and winter. In truth I tell you that no small bird, as quick as it may go flurrying about, would never be able to get into the palace without being killed; it would not succeed in getting through» [in the original French text: «Et s'a deux hommes à l'entrer de l'ostel; Tout sont de keuvre et fait et compasé, Si tient cascuns un flaiel acouplé, Tout sont de fer, moult font à redouter. Tout adès batent et yver et esté, Et si vous di, par fine verité, Une aloete, que bien tost set voler, Ne poroit mie ens el palais voler Que ne fust morte; ne poroit escaper»].

That's very, very similar to the account written by de la Sale about Mount Sibyl: a comparable metal device, in a perpetual motion, lashing to and from, and preventing the access to men; small animals (birds, flies) used as an example to show the potential crushing effect on a daring visitor.

Is that all? No. Because if we take another earlier chivalric poem, *Huon d'Auvergne*, we find another comparable episode, this time set by the castle of Lucifer:

«A lofty palace, with a tower standing before it,
Not made of stone as towers are used to be made;
That is made of metal, and tempered iron;
High walls are around the palace,
A front gate guarded by two lions,
And the gate is such
That as soon as it is swung open,
No blade is as sharp as the gate itself,
the doors cutting easily and sweetly;
they just keep on opening up and shutting close».

[in the original French-Italian text:
«Alto è el pallaço, una tore davanti li à,
No è de piere como le tore se fa,
Ançy è d'açalle e de fero tenperà;
Alti son li muri ch'el palaço cricundà,
Davanti à una porta che do lion guardà,
E quele porte tal natura si à
Si tosto como elle averte incontenente se serà,
El non è raxori tanto taianti e filà
Che taia cossì soave como quele porte fa;
De serar e de avre alltro elle non fa».]

Again: an ever-slamming metal gate, as sharp as a razor, preventing any undesired visitor to sneak in. Doesn't it sound as the very same contrivance as described by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*?

It begins to be clear to us that the fabulous «metal doors, which slam ceaselessly day and night» mentioned in *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* as concealed within the bosom of Mount Sibyl, Italy, have never been there, because they do not belong to any local, original lore concerning the Apennine Sibyl.

Antoine de la Sale drew those doors from earlier literary accounts and put them into his narration to please his highborn audience, and fill their hearts,

as experienced writers use to do, with wonder and surprise. Just like the magical narrow bridge with variable width we have considered in a previous article.

But where did he take the metal doors from?

If we look at the *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii* (“Essay on the Purgatory of St. Patrick”), the ancient Irish legend reported in twelfth-century manuscripts - which we saw bearing mention of the famous bridge for testing the purity of souls - we find something that seems to be similar, though not fully alike:

«He saw before him a huge wheel made of iron and fire, whose spokes and rim were entirely encircled with fiery hooks, to each of which single hanging men were stuck. [...] And the fiends [...] made the wheel go upwards. On the other side, other demons [...] pushed it downwards and made it turn around so quick that it was hardly visible» [in the original Latin text: «Vidit ante se maximam rotam ferream et igneam, cujus radii et canti unciis igneis undique erant circumfecti, in quibus singulis pendebant quasi homines infixi. [...] Demones igitur [...] rotam levaverunt. Alii ex alia parte [...] deorsum depresserunt tantaque eam agilitate fecerunt rotare, ut nullus omnino alium posset discernere»].

In the *Purgatory of St. Patrick*, the above episode is marked by a few peculiar aspects: a metallic device, a rotating mechanism, of such a kind that it never stops its evil gyration. A contrivance imagined by God to punish the sinners in Hell. And a suspicious connection to similar aspect we have already found in Antoine de la Sale's work.

But if we look for a conclusive clue, we have to turn to the *Vision of St. Adamnán*, an eleventh-century account written in the *Lebor na hUidre*, the “Book of the Dun Cow”, an ancient Irish manuscript. We already saw that it contains the same magically narrow bridge described by Antoine de la Sale as spanning across an abyss within the cave of the Apennine Sibyl. And not only this: it also contains very interesting special doors, protecting the entrance to the city of the Land of Saints:

«In the main doorway of the city they are confronted by a veil of fire and a veil of ice, smiting perpetually one against the other. The noise and din of

these veils, as they clash together, are heard throughout the world, and the seed of Adam, should they hear that din, would be seized thereat with trembling and intolerable dismay».

[In the original Irish text: «Fíal tened ocus fíal d'aigriud i prímdorus inna cathrac inna fíadnaisse...»]

Again, here is the same idea of a clashing barrier that never stops its malignant motion, to avoid any attempt at entering a forbidden place.

Now a question arises: where do the “clashing doors” come from? Where have we to direct our search so as to identify the original source of this amazing, fascinating myth?

In the next paragraph, we will continue our fantastic journey into this legendary image, leaving Antoine de la Sale and the otherworldly visions of the Middle Ages behind, and, through the Arthurian literary cycle, we will go as far as the antique, classical world. A travel that will lead our search toward the original source of a legend: the magical slamming doors.

2. The Apennine Sibyl, King Arthur and the magical passages to unearthly realms

Magical metal doors slamming day and night in Antoine de la Sale's work on the Apennine Sibyl. Bronze men who hold scourges lashing throughout summers and winters in the chivalric poem *Huon de Bordeaux*. An ever-slaming gate as sharp as a razor in *Huon d'Auvergne*. Veils of fire and ice smiting perpetually one against the other in the ancient *Vision of St. Adamnán* Irish manuscript.

A dangerous passage. A point of transition between our world, inhabited by mortal beings, and magical, supernatural realms. A threat for all venturesome visitors who dare to cross such forbidden borders, which are only open to pure, uncorrupted souls.

Where does all that come from? Where is to be found the ultimate literary origin of the very special doors that, in the fifteenth century, Antoine de la

Sale wanted to include in his compelling narration about the realm of the Apennine Sibyl?

They come from very, very far. And made a very long travel through history.

As we described in a previous article, we find the footprints of the magical, ever-slamming perilous passage throughout the European literature of the Middle Ages and beyond: *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, *Huon of Bordeaux*, *Huon d'Auvergne*, the *Vision of St. Adamnán*.

Remarkably enough, other peculiar instances can be traced in the Arthurian literary cycle. A thirteenth-century manuscript (Bern, Burgerbibliothek, Cod. 354) contains *La Mule sens Frein* (or “The Lady with the Mule”), a French romance where Gawain, a knight at the court of King Arthur, confronts with a very special castle, a revolving one:

«He couldn't see a gate or door.
The castle was whirling
As fast as a racing mill wheel
Or like a top that had been
Spun from its cord [...]
The castle was whirling unceasingly [...]
He chose his time carefully [...]
So as soon as he saw the gate coming,
He spurred his mule sharply [...]
And raced through the gate»

[In the original French text:
«Ne huis ne porte n'i avoit.
Li chastiax si fort tornoioit
Con muele de molin qui muet,
Et con la trompe que l'en suet
A la corgiee demener [...]
Li chastiax tot ades tornoie [...]
Mout a bien son point esgardé [...]
Atant voit la porte venir,
Si point la mule de randon [...]
Si s'est en la porte ferue»].

Gawain enters a forbidden place, in which he will be challenged by a fiendish character, after a rush through a narrow, dangerous passage in a perpetual motion: a wizardry that only a brave and unblemished soul may try to overcome.

In the Arthurian cycle, the variant of a perilous passage portrayed as a “revolving castle” is present in a number of additional instances. Let's take, for instance, *The High History of the Holy Grail (Li Hauz Livres du Graal)*, a romance written in old French at the beginning of the thirteenth century. In Chapter XVII, dedicated to the Holy Grail, the knights Gawain, Lancelot and Perceval arrive to a fortress, the Castle of Great Endeavour («le chastel de Grant Esfort»). And the entranceway to the castle is an ever-turning, dangerous gate:

«They draw nigh the castle and see that it turned all about faster than the wind may run [...] With that he [Perceval] smote with his spurs and went his way to the castle as fast as his horse may carry him, toward the Turning Castle. He struck with his sword at the gate so strongly that he cut a good three fingers into a shaft of marble [... and] he was beyond».

[In the original French text: «Il aprochent le chastel et voient qu'il tornoie tout environ plus tost que vet ne court [...] Perceval] atant fiert des esperons et s'an vet vers le chastel tant conme li chevaus li peut randre, vers le chastel tornoient. Il fiert de l'espee à la porte si très durement que il l'an ferra bien trois doie en un piler de marbre [... et] il fu outre»].

Other revolving castles, with their hard-to-go-through gates providing a magical access to forbidden places, can be found in ancient Irish legends, such as the one reported in the *Bricriu's Feast (Fled Bricreinn* in Old Irish): «... every night over the fort he chaunted a spell, till the fort revolved as swiftly as a mill-stone. The entrance was never to be found after sunset...».

What have the revolving castle got to do with the Apennine Sibyl's doors in a perpetual motion described by Antoine de la Sale?

A close connection can be traced between the two types of hazardous gates, the slamming and the revolving: in his book *Gawain and the Green Knight*, Professor G. L. Kittredge states that «the whirling castle belongs to the

same general category as perpetually slamming doors». The doors in the Sibyl's cave, the castle of Gawain: they are linked by a same idea of an hazardous passageway, a narrow escape into a different magical or supernatural place.

Looking for another example of the dangerous passageway in the Arthurian cycle? We don't need to go any farther. Let's stick to *The High History of the Holy Grail* and read the chapter following the adventures of our brave knight Perceval at the Castle of Great Endeavour. He continues his journey on horseback until he gets to the Castle of Copper.

The Castle of Copper: a very special place. Because there we find something that we have already encountered in the tales on the Apennine Sibyl:

«At the entrance to the gateway of the castle were two men made by art of necromancy, and they held two great mallets of iron, and they busied themselves striking the one after the other, and so strongly they struck that nought mortal is there in the world that might pass through amongst their blows but should be all to-crushed thereby. [... A Voice told him not to be afraid as] no power had they to harm such a knight as was he. He comforted himself much of that the Voice said to him. He comes near to the serjeants of copper, and they cease to strike at once, and hold their iron mallets quite still. And he entered into the castle».

[In the Old French text: «A l'entrée de la porte del chastel avoit deux homes fez part l'art de nigromence, si tenoient deus gros maus de fer, si s'acoupoient de férir li uns après l'autre, et feroient si très durement qu'il n'est riens mortel el monde, qui péust passer parmi lor cox, qui touz ne fust confinduz. [... Une voix lui dit de ne pas s'épouvanter parce-que] il n'avoient pover de mal feire si bon chevalier cnme il estoit. Il se conforte mout en ce que la voiz li dit; il s'aproche des vileins de coivre, et il se targent tantost de férir, et se tiennent les max de fer touz coiz; et il entre el chastel»].

That was another perilous passage, this time made up with ever-hammering mallets (not dissimilar from the scourges appearing in *Huon de Bordeaux*).

And what do we find inside the castle? Here is what *The High History of the Holy Grail* says:

«There was an evil spirit within that gave answers concerning whatsoever any should ask of it» («avoit mauveiz esperiz dedanz qui lor donnoient respons de quanque il onques vouloient demander»).

Something inside. That rendered oracular response to its visitors. An evil spirit that seems to be very similar to an Apennine Sibyl. And protected by a very same ever-moving device, metal doors for the Sibyl, hammers for the Castle of Copper (note that metal appears in both tales, as in many other instances which narrate of perilous passageways).

Thus, this is a further confirmation - if needed - of the indubitable fact that Antoine de la Sale was neither original nor sincere when he decided to include the ever-slamming metal doors in his description of the Paradise of Queen Sibyl, well buried under the flanks of Mount Sibyl in Italy. He just copied from a long-established tradition of hazardous gates and passageways, which a hero with an uncorrupted soul would confront with when trying to attain a magical, supernatural place.

Fig. 2 - A miniature showing the metal doors beneath Mount Sibyl taken from Manuscript no. 653 preserved at the Bibliothèque du Musée Condé in Chantilly (France) containing *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* by Antoine de la Sale

And there is more to that. Because we need to go back to our fundamental question: where do the doors, and scourges and veils of ice and fire, and revolving castles, and hammers, all in a never-stopping motion, come from?

The answer is in Professor Kittredge's sentence, for he continues his statement by saying that the revolving castle and the ever-slamming doors belong to the same category as the «clashing cliffs (symplegades)».

The Symplegades, the clashing cliffs. The original source of a myth that Antoine de la Sale included in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, through the mediation of a world of chivalric poems and romances and visionary tales of the otherworld. A myth that originates in classical Greece, and is rooted in legendary tales of heroes, perilous travels and journeys into the otherworld.

As we will see in the next paragraph.

3. Antoine de la Sale and the ancient Greek myth of Symplegades

On May, 18th 1420, Antoine de la Sale, a gentleman and man of letter from Provence, ascended Mount Sibyl in Italy and visited the already famous Cave of the Apennine Sibyl. Many years later, he wrote an account of his journey to such a remote region of Italy. And, to please his audience of courtly ladies, he added a few literary strokes to his picturesque painting.

One of those strokes was the magical narrow bridge, an unearthly contrivance which - as we already saw in previous articles - was drawn by the experienced writer from an antique tradition of test bridges encountered in many medieval descriptions of travels into the otherworld.

With his literary brush, he painted another brilliant stroke when he mentioned the appalling ever-slamming metal doors, hindering day and night, with their perpetual, automated motion, the passage to visitors lacking enough courage to cope with their eerie challenge.

We have demonstrated that the doors too belong to an illustrious ancestral lineage of dreadful literary contrivances opening their threatening jaws to admit brave, unblemished hearts into enchanted or otherworldly regions: from *Huon of Bordeaux* to *Huon d'Auvergne*, from the *Vision of St. Adamnán* to the “revolving castles” of the Arthurian cycle, we find a variety of metal doors, lashing scourges, veils of fire and ice, rotating gates, all in a rapid motion intended to shield the access to a magical or supernatural place located beyond the wizardly obstacle.

But where does it all come from? Where may we find the original prototype of the ever-moving barriers, the grim perilous passages that only true heroes can go through and overcome?

We have to turn to ancient Greece. Because, as illustrious scholars have stated, all the listed literary devices belong to the same category as the «clashing cliffs (symplegades)».

The Symplegades. The ever-clashing rocks. The gate that cannot be trespassed if you are not accompanied through it by the hand of a God.

Let's listen to the antique words of Apollonius of Rhodes, an author who lived during the third century B.C., the head of the Library of Alexandria in his time, and most renowned for his epic poem *Argonautica*, from which we quote (Book II, 581 ff.):

«When they reached the narrow strait [...] they went forward sorely in dread; and now the thud of the crashing rocks ceaselessly struck their ears [...] And as they rounded a bend they saw the rocks opening for the last time of all. Their spirit melted within them, and Euphemus sent forth the dove to dart forward in flight [...] she flew between them, and the rocks again rushed together and crashed as they met face to face [...] and then the rocks shore away the end of the dove's tail-feathers; but away she flew unscathed [...]».

The Argonauts, their ship, their daring travel to reach Colchis and the Golden Fleece. A perilous passage, found in a very specific location: at the very entrance of the Black Sea, where the Strait of Bosphorus provides an entrance to that large internal sea. Jason and his crew must go through it on their way to Colchis, but who may ever pass this magical obstacle?

Only a God will be able to help them:

«[...] the eddying current held the ship between the clashing rocks; and on each side they shook and thundered [...] But Euphemus strode among all his comrades and cried to them to bend to their oars with all their might [...] Then Athena with her left hand thrust back one mighty rock and with her right pushed the ship through. Nevertheless the rocks, ceaselessly clashing, shore off as she passed the extreme end of the stern-ornament [...] And the heroes breathed again after their chilling fear, for they deemed that they were saved from Hades».

Fig. 3 - A seventeenth-century print showing the ship Argo as it passes through the clashing rocks of Symplegades, preserved at the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York

That's the original specimen of all clashing doors and scourges and veils and rotating castles. The Symplegades: a myth and a literary image so powerful that it has crossed thousands of years, transforming itself under different shapes so as to adapt to a number of poetic situations and heroic quests.

Until the myth fell into the hands of Antoine de la Sale, through a number of literary mediations: he decided to add it to his description of a magical subterranean realm concealed beneath Mount Sibyl. A travel into the otherworld, where supernaturally narrow bridges and ever-clashing devices have belonged since the earliest ages of man.

A. B. Cook, in his *Zeus, a Study in Ancient Religion*, says that the Symplegades «presuppose the ancient popular belief in a doorway to the Otherworld formed by clashing mountain-walls». And in the beautiful essay written by A. K. Coomaraswamy, *Symplegades*, the great scholar expressed in a most effective way what «the full doctrinal significance of the Symplegades» is in the history of culture:

«Whoever would transfer from this to the Otherworld, or return, must do so through the undimensioned and timeless "interval" that divides related but contrary forces, between which, if one is to pass at all, it must be "instantly". The passage is, of course, that which is also called the "strait gate" and the "needle's eye." [These are] contraries, of which the operation is "automatic" [...] It is, then, precisely from these "pairs" that liberation must be won, from their conflict that we must escape, if we are to be freed from our mortality and to be as and when we will: if, in other words, we are to reach the Farther Shore and Otherworld».

The clashing rocks - just like the magically narrow bridges - belong to the most ancient ideas ever developed by man in his struggle to understand life and death. And it is Coomaraswamy himself that introduces to us the same kind of “clashing” visions, this time drawn from the earliest oriental mythology.

So to our bewildered gaze, Antoine de la Sale's ever-clashing device begins to emerge from an ever remoter past: in the *Satapatha Brâhmana*, a text in Sanskrit dating back to the eighth century B.C., where we find «two golden leaves, that were razor-edged, and snapped together at every winking of an

eye»; and in the *Suparnadhyaya*, an ancient Vedic text, which describes «two sleepless, watchful, razor-edged lightnings, striking from every side».

Therefore, no ever-slamming doors ever existed in the original, local lore concerning a Sibyl of the Apennines living beneath Mount Sibyl. Antoine de la Sale just added them to his account *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, drawing inspiration from a number of magical clashing devices that have crossed the Eastern and Western literature since many centuries before the advent of Christ.

We stress the fundamental point that this result - together with a similar one already ascertained with regard to the magically narrow test-bridge we described in previous articles - has never been stated before: only “The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend” has been able to unveil the true origin of the descriptions included by Antoine de la Sale in his work on the Sibyl. They belong to other, dissimilar traditional tales, and they have nothing to do with the true sibilline legend. This is no wonder to us: as already noted by Patrizia Romagnoli, a Swiss scholar and the Italian translator of *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, «thanks to Antoine de la Sale, the dark tale is turned into a refined narration for a courtly audience, suitable for the time of leisure amid charming companions». In this view, each section of the tale can be «of significance as to the rythm of the narration, a fictitious and recreational space».

So what's now standing ahead of us? New astounding landscapes seem to open before our very eyes.

In fact, these remarkable results now provide us with a major clue: the original core of the legend of the Apennine Sibyl is not hidden in Antoine de la Sale's text, which contains a number of literary overlays belonging to other traditions.

Now we know that the true core of the Apennine Sibyl's legend lies elsewhere. And we are about to formulate an absolutely new theory about the origin of the legend and lore that has enshrouded with eerie mystery the lonely cavern on the cliff of Mount Sibil, Italy, for centuries and centuries.

A theory, based on the results we have just outlined and further original studies, that no one has ever stated before. A theory that will open a brand new line of research concerning the ancient myth of the Apennine Sibyl.

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